

Natural Extract-Based Strategies for Improving the Biological Resistance of Bamboo

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Abstract

Bamboo is one of Nepal's most versatile and sustainable natural resources, traditionally used in housing, scaffolding, bridges, tools, and handicrafts. With its rapid growth and high strength-to-weight ratio, it has significant potential as a modern construction material and as a substitute for non-renewable resources.

However, bamboo's wider adoption is hindered by its susceptibility to biological degradation. Fungal attack causes staining, softening, and reduced mechanical integrity, while termite infestation leads to rapid structural failure. These vulnerabilities shorten service life and undermine confidence in bamboo as a reliable building material. In Nepal, this challenge is further complicated by limited treatment facilities, dependence on imported chemical preservatives, and inadequate awareness about preservation practices.

This study investigates the use of locally available plant extracts as eco-friendly and cost-effective alternatives to conventional chemicals. Different plant extracts with proven antifungal and insect-repellent properties, are evaluated for their potential to extend bamboo's durability. Developing such sustainable treatment methods will not only enhance the structural performance of bamboo but also reduce environmental risks and reliance on synthetic chemicals.

By combining traditional knowledge with scientific approaches, this research underscores bamboo's dual role in Nepal: as a cultural resource with deep-rooted uses and as a modern, sustainable construction material. Eco-friendly preservation strategies can strengthen rural livelihoods, promote green infrastructure, and support long-term forest resource management.

Keywords: *bamboo preservation, plant extracts, fungal degradation, termite resistance, sustainable construction*